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Deliverable D2.1

EMAI4EU self-standing modules: Market analysis and curriculum design

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the results of Task 2.1 within Work Package 2 of the *EMAI4EU – Emotion Artificial Intelligence Specialists for Europe* project. It combines a market analysis on the demand for Emotion AI skills in Europe with the design of the first set of Self-Standing Learning Modules (SSLMs).

The analysis, based on 151 responses from individuals and companies, confirmed strong interest in AI and Emotion AI training, particularly in fields such as customer experience, healthcare, education, and human resources. The findings guided the definition of a modular and flexible curriculum, divided into basic and advanced certification paths.

The developed modules provide interdisciplinary and ethically grounded training opportunities that complement the EMAI4EU Master's programme and support Europe's goals for human-centric and responsible AI education.

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Executive Summary

Task 2.1 aimed to conduct a market analysis to assess the demand for Emotion AI, identify skill needs, and inform the design of self-standing learning modules (SSLMs). The task involved collecting market insights from both industry representatives and individual learners (e.g. students, professionals) via questionnaire conducted between June 2025 to August 2025. This approach ensured that the design of AI and Emotion AI SSLMs aligns with current market needs. To broaden perspectives, new contacts such as individual learners were included in this round of data collection.

The market analysis drew 151 responses. The results indicated high demand for AI and Emotion AI training. Among individual respondents, 79 % expressed interest in AI training and 67 % in Emotion AI training. Similarly, 78 % of company respondents are interested in AI training and 56 % in Emotion AI. The most frequently cited barriers to undertaking additional training for AI and Emotion AI were time and resources.

43% of individual respondents and 51% of company respondents believe that Emotion AI will become increasingly important in the future. While companies recognize its potential, most have not yet integrated Emotion AI technology into their business operations due to competing priorities.

The most desired skills of an Emotion AI specialist include human psychology understanding, emotion recognition, empathy development, ethical decision-making, communication skills, and natural language processing. The most relevant application areas identified were customer experience and satisfaction, healthcare, education and human resources. These highlight the Emotion AI's potential for improving customer satisfaction, increasing engagement, enabling personalized interactions, and enhancing the user experience.

For the format of SSLMs, respondents preferred short videos, slides or lecture notes, and continuous assessment as the main learning formats. To address time and resource constraints, a flexible certification structure was introduced. Learners can earn micro credentials from completing individual SSLMs or full certifications. The modules are divided in two certification paths, basic and advanced.

The final list of modules was developed based on the previous WP1 market analysis, questionnaire results, and internal needs. Additional modules were added to the final list

of modules to address the need for comprehensive introduction to the topic and using Emotion AI for UI/UX.

The consortium will implement continuous monitoring of learner feedback to guide future updates and ensure that the modules remain relevant to evolving market needs.

1. Introduction

The EMAI4EU project aims to fill the gap created by the increasing use of artificial intelligence in the labour market, in higher education, and in a wide range of applications from medicine to industrial quality control, in various automation, diagnostic, and user-assistance applications.

The objectives of the second work package are: (1) to develop self-standing learning modules addressing Europe's skill needs in AI and Emotion AI, and (2) to deliver self-standing learning modules leading to certifications and contribute to training Emotion AI specialists across Europe.

This report presents the results of the second work package (WP2) of the EMAI4EU project which focused on self-standing learning modules. The current documentation is divided into two main parts. The first major section assesses the market needs for the online self-standing learning modules (SSLMs) related to emotion artificial intelligence (AI). The second major section contains the consortium's contribution and details about the creation and documentation of the first set of identified self-standing learning modules. This initial set will be subject to revisions in the remaining years of the project where the contents will undergo periodic review and new courses will also be added.

Beyond the traditional education setting [1], online courses are one of the primary providers of ***lifelong learning***, which is widespread in professionally conscious societies [2]. The following online platforms are the most popular course providers:

- Coursera (American, founded in 2012) [3]
- EdX (American, founded in 2012) [4]
- Udemy (American, founded in 2010) [5]
- Skillshare (American, founded in 2010) [6]
- Udacity (American, founded in 2011) [7]

- LinkedIn Learning Links (American, founded in 1995 as Lynda.com) [8]
- FutureLearn, (British, founded in 2012) [9]

The list shows that most of these online education platforms were launched around the 2010s and were created in the United States. Without going into the details and specifics of these providers, it can be said that the available courses cover a wide range of topics, such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, computer vision, programming, finance, arts, sciences (physics, chemistry, biology), economics, management, and other soft skills. The providers come from both the industrial and academic sectors.

Searching for the term "emotional artificial intelligence" on such platforms is not an easy task. Most recommendations relate to topics such as "emotional intelligence," "emotion regulation," and "emotions and leadership," which are clearly not the same as the goal of EMAI4EU. The consortium recognized that explaining and promoting "emotional artificial intelligence" is a challenging task not only for students but also for company representatives. The questionnaires show that emotional artificial intelligence does not have a clear and popularly understood recognition.

The consortium's solution and long-term plan is to promote the innovation potential of emotional artificial intelligence and to provide innovative education through online courses. The chosen platform is ICARUS Education (provided by EIT Digital [10]), and all related courses are labeled EMAI4EU, which facilitates searching and brings the courses together for better visibility.

Upskilling and re-skilling expertise, and even acquiring new knowledge, is not only a universal human need, but also a natural reaction to the rapidly changing job environment. The demand for self-improvement has clearly not decreased in recent decades, but rather increased. There are many motivations for developing skills, such as improving soft skills and leadership competences for career advancement, acquiring specialised knowledge to explore new professional fields, or even acquiring basic digital skills to keep up with the times, especially with the rise of AI.

Job satisfaction is key to the success of any business. Employee satisfaction can be achieved by providing professional advancement, development opportunities, and challenges [11].

Whether chosen by employees for personal motivation or supported by employers, online courses offer convenient and wide-ranging opportunities for self-development. Numerous paid and free courses are available on the platforms mentioned above [3-9].

The courses developed by the consortium under EMAI4EU will remain available free of charge for the duration of the project and will be reviewed over time.

Supporting the demand for AI and emotional AI professionals in Europe should not only be based on traditional academic education (covered by WP1 of the EMAI4EU project), but also on these more flexible and targeted online courses, which is the goal of WP2. The market analysis chapter presents the process of collecting feedback from industry stakeholders and higher education students. Subsequently, the results are presented with visual illustrations of each section of the questionnaire (AI, emotional AI, needs, and training topics). Finally, this chapter highlights important conclusions drawn from the questionnaire results that influenced the final set of self-standing learning modules.

The second main chapter covers the design of the SSLM curriculum, the final list of developed SSLMs, details of the structure of the templates, micro-modules, grading and assessment methods, certificates, long-term plans, and conclusions. The subsections describe in detail the entire process from initial planning to final development, which is firmly based on the results of the questionnaire and reflects the needs of the market and individuals in the field of artificial intelligence and emotional artificial intelligence.

2. Market analysis

2.1. Introduction

A market analysis was conducted to understand the skills needs of Europe in AI and Emotion AI with particular focus on the needs of companies and individuals regarding Emotion AI online training. In the first year, for WP1 Master's Program and WP2 Self Standing Learning Modules market analyses were jointly conducted to gather an initial idea of the market needs that could inform a primary definition of the master's degree curricula. The learnings from this first cycle deploying questionnaires and the results of market analysis were used by the team to devise a revised version of the questionnaire to target more precisely companies and individuals aiming to acquire competencies and skills on Emotion AI.

Therefore, this market analysis builds on the WP1 market analysis previously conducted for the Emotion AI Master's degree program. WP1 market analysis results had already showed the need to add new possible modules to the curriculum. The identified needs

included modules that provide a solid foundation for all the learners and understand the future applications of Emotion AI. The additional modules are:

- *Introduction to Emotion AI,*
- *Using Emotion AI for UI/UX*
- *Future of Emotion AI*
- *Innovation and Entrepreneurship*
- *Corporate Engagement*
- *Emotion and Multimodal Foundation Models*

2.2. Questionnaire design

Since the self-standing modules target a broad audience, from individuals without a technological background to IT professionals looking to upskill or reskill in AI and Emotion AI, the WP1 questionnaire was revised. From originally focusing on companies, this was adapted to address the needs of individual learners as well, such as students and professionals from both technical and non-technical domains. The questionnaire was therefore divided into two branches: one for individuals and one for company representatives.

The WP1 market analysis questionnaire was used as a template for the WP2 questionnaire. Questions that were not relevant to WP2 were removed such as those about the risks of AI. In addition, new questions were added on topics such as the content of the self-standing modules, certificates, learning paths, and pricing.

The consortium developed an initial version of the questionnaire, which underwent a pilot testing phase to ensure that the questions were clear, the response options comprehensive, and that it adequately met the project's needs. Ludotic managed this phase, conducting three one-hour interviews with individuals from different profiles (Purchasing, HR, and Development), employed at companies of varying sizes (Amadeus, a large international group; Orange, a major French company; and One Corp, an SME in the IT sector). These interviews allowed us to gather all the necessary feedback and refine the questions to better capture the needs of the different respondent profiles before a broader rollout.

At the beginning of the questionnaire, respondents can select which role they wish to answer the questionnaire. The introduction and conclusion are the same for both branches. Selecting the "individual" path leads the respondent to sections 2A General information, 3A

Emotion AI, 4A Training, and finally the conclusion. Selecting the "company representative" path leads the respondent to sections 2B General information, 3B Emotion AI, 4B Needs and priorities, 5B Training, and finally the conclusion. The complete questionnaire structure is provided in Appendix 1.

Depending on the content of the question, single-choice, multiple-choice, or Likert scale solutions were implemented to collect feedback. In terms of the structure of the 7-point Likert scale, each statement has a numbered scale where 1 and 7 represent the negative and positive end-values, with a neutral rating in the middle. We supplemented this with a "I don't know" option to obtain more accurate values.

In the evaluation, we took into account the number of responses given to each Likert point, calculated basic statistics, and summarized them in the relevant sections of the report.

2.3. Methods

The questionnaire was conducted using Microsoft Forms. It was most suitable for a questionnaire that needed to be divided into two different branches, without being too complicated to use.

The team created invitation letter templates to reach out to individuals and companies. These included versions for new individuals and company contacts, as well as for existing company contacts used during the WP1 market analysis. Since we reused many of the same contacts from WP1, recipients from the previous questionnaire were also provided a summary of the results. Consortium partners were free to adapt the templates as needed for their contacts, including translating them into other languages.

Company representatives were directly approached via email and through mailing lists. In total, approximately 213 companies and partner networks were contacted through partner networks and mailing lists, some of whom further shared the questionnaire within their own networks. Each project partner promoted the questionnaire to their local industrial contacts directly or through associations of companies (e.g., Confindustria for Italy). To reach a large community, the questionnaire was also promoted on LinkedIn. In addition, approximately 854 master's and PhD students were reached via email. Contacting and advertising began on June 6, 2025, and continued through August 2025. The consortium partners received weekly updates on the status of questionnaire responses, and the preliminary results were discussed in the periodic WP meetings.

In the end, the final results were analysed using descriptive statistics provided by the Microsoft Forms platform and through a qualitative analysis of the open-ended questions.

2.4. Results and analysis

2.4.1. General overview

Partners collected 151 responses to the questionnaire of which 106 came from individuals and 45 from companies. Among individual respondents, the most common roles were student (25%), project manager (13%), other (12%), and UX design/researcher (8%). The category "other" consisted mostly of PhD students or researchers. For company respondents, the three most common roles were C-level/top management (29%), management and general administration (16%), and project manager (13%).

Regarding sectors, the most common sector of activities among individual respondents were information technology and communication (25%), education (15%), other (13%), and healthcare and pharmaceuticals (11%) and manufacturing industry (11%). Among company representatives the most common sector of activities were: information technology and communication (47%) and other (16%). These companies were mostly small, with 44% having 1-20 employees and 36 % having 21-99 employees.

2.4.2. Use of AI

From the individual respondents, nearly all of them use AI tools for work (94%). Many use text generation tools, such as ChatGPT (36%). The other most popular AI tools include different search engines (21%) and AI programming tools (18%).

Similarly, almost all the company representatives use AI tools for their work tasks (93%), though the specific tools they use differ from those of individual respondents. They use text generation (36%), search engines (18%), and image generation (15%).

The team asked from the company respondents about their company's level of AI integration. The answers tended to fall within the range of 1-5 meaning that AI integration in the companies is not that high. The exported visualisation from the Microsoft Forms can be seen on Figure 1.

33. Is your company currently using any AI technology? Please rate your company's current level of AI integration on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not currently using' and 7 means 'Fully integrated'.

Figure 1: Level of AI integration in companies

2.4.3. Emotion AI

55% of individual and 58% of company representatives had heard of Emotion AI before. This is an important factor to consider when analysing the responses, especially those related to the importance of different skills for Emotion AI specialists. However, it may highlight the need for these skills in the companies and in general.

Individual respondents expressed mixed opinions about the future popularity of Emotion AI technology. However, more respondents agreed (43%) than disagreed (31%) that it will become more popular. A notable amount (16%) also answered "I don't know". Company representatives tended to be more positive, many (51%) believing the technology will become more important in the future, but still significant number of answers (24%) in the lower end of the scale. Exported data is presented on Figure 2.

35. Emotion AI technology will become increasingly important in my sector over the next few years. Please rate your level of agreement on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Strongly disagree' and 7 means 'Strongly agree'.

Figure 2: Companies perceived importance of Emotion AI

Emotion AI is not a high priority for companies, which is not surprising given that many respondents were unfamiliar with the concept. 51% of company representatives responded that it is a low priority. However, some respondents said they could use it for customer service or other customer related activities. Companies view Emotion AI as beneficial, for example, for improving their customer satisfaction, increasing engagement, enabling personalized interactions, and enhancing the user experience. More details are shown in Figure 3.

40. What potential benefits do you foresee from using Emotion AI technologies in your business operations? (Select all that apply)

Figure 3: Potential benefits of Emotion AI in business operations

According to the company representatives, when asked where Emotion AI could have a significant impact beyond their own company, they most often mentioned areas such as education, customer related activities, and healthcare.

Among companies, 53 % were unsure whether they would like to have Emotion AI specialists in their company and 27 % said they would not like to have. The most common reason cited for not wanting an Emotion AI specialist in their company was that they have other priorities. 20 % said they would like to have Emotion AI specialist in their company.

Both individuals and company representatives tended to fall on the neutral and positive side when asked whether they perceive Emotion AI as a technological bubble or an asset to society. Overall, more respondents consider Emotion AI to be a valuable asset rather than a technological bubble.

2.4.4. AI and Emotion AI needs

Responses regarding interest in AI and Emotion AI training indicate a positive level of interest among both individual and company respondents. 79 % of individuals would be personally interested in AI related training and 67 % would be interested in Emotion AI training. 78 % of company representatives would be personally interested in AI related training and 56 % would be interested in Emotion AI training. Many individuals cited lack of time and resources as the main obstacles for acquiring more AI training.

AI training is considered relevant to companies' goals, but when asked about the relevance of Emotion AI training the responses were more evenly distributed across the scale. Detailed visualisation is shown on Figure 4.

50. How relevant is Emotion AI training for your company's goals? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not relevant' and 7 means 'Very relevant'.

Figure 4: Relevance of Emotion AI training for companies' goals

Learning paths that address different skill levels, technical aspects, applied use cases, and role-specific topics were considered equally important by individual responders, each receiving about 25 % of the responses. Company representatives, however, leaned more towards learning paths focused on different skill levels (34%) and applied use cases (29%).

Case studies are popular and useful training tools, and their relevance and practicality also attract businesses. Although a learning path may require more time and energy from the employee or student, the more comprehensive knowledge gained is worth the effort invested. Acquiring comprehensive expertise also means that participants can apply their knowledge in a more flexible and creative manner, which is a clear advantage from the perspective of companies' upskilling strategies.

All the modules and their titles were listed to the questionnaire, and respondents were asked to rate the importance of each for inclusion in the Emotion AI online training. Both individual and company respondents considered *Semantic Web Technologies*, *Basics of Data Analysis*, and *Deep Network Development* to be the least important topics.

It is worth noting that although basic data analysis and deep network development have not gained popularity in terms of their names or perceived content, they nevertheless form the solid scientific basis of the AI specialist profession.

In contrast, topics such as *Introduction to Emotion AI*, *Human-Machine Socio-Emotional Interaction*, *Cognitive Science*, *Emotional Human-Robot Interaction*, and *Creating Value for Humans Through AI* were among the most desired. This trend is visible across the results. For the results of the individual respondents, refer to Figure 5.

21. How important do you consider each of the following topics for Emotion AI online course? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.

Figure 5: Importance of topics for Emotion AI online course

Completing the aforementioned courses (see Figure 5) contributes to the development of multiple skills. To assess the order of importance of these skills, we included a question (Q11) asking respondents to rate them. These types of skills both consider competencies of "human skills" (human psychology understanding, empathy development, communication, etc.) and capabilities that are related to basic, computer science-based topics (such as computer vision, machine learning, data engineering etc.). The visual representation can be seen in Figure 6. It shows that the skills are closely related to the most demanded topics.

11. How important do you consider each of the following skills for an Emotion AI specialist? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.

Figure 6: Importance of skills for Emotion AI specialist

Based on the results, the modules were refined to better align with stakeholders needs. The results also influenced the next stage of module development, which is discussed in the following section 2.5.

2.4.5. Training delivery

Both individuals and company representatives prefer blended learning (synchronous and asynchronous) and asynchronous delivery methods. Both individuals and company representatives consider Q&A sessions to be extremely to somewhat valuable. The preferred assessment method of the modules are continuous quizzes, as well as a combination of continuous quizzes and final exams.

Regarding the course materials, both individual and company representatives prefer short video and slides and lecture notes. Individual respondents also showed considerable interest in code examples and articles/reading list, which are not far from the two most chosen options.

Both individual and company representatives prefer one-time payment and subscription as the possible pricing model of the online course. The amount of money respondents are willing to pay depends on the value and content of the course. The second most answers being 0-25 euros (18%) for individuals and 51-200 euros (20%) for company representatives.

Certifications are important for both parties. The preferred certifications are industry-recognized or university-issued certifications.

According to the questionnaire's free-text responses, respondents highlighted that additional information on the risks of Emotion AI, relevant policies and laws, and cultural differences is important when considering the technology.

2.5. Implication for self-standing modules

When comparing the results with the WP1 market analysis, it can be seen there is still strong demand for AI and Emotion AI training. In this questionnaire, we also included additional contacts, such as students and individual industry professionals to broaden the perspectives represented in the results. Very few companies have yet integrated Emotion AI into their business operations, but many recognise Emotion AI technology becoming an increasingly important area. Especially areas such as customer support and customer experience are frequently mentioned in the results as potential use cases. The results between the two questionnaires are mostly consistent. While general AI and machine learning skills remain relevant, both questionnaire results highlight skills like human psychology understanding, emotion recognition, and ethical considerations.

When identifying potential application areas for Emotion AI technology, customer service and satisfaction, healthcare, education, and human resources emerged as the most relevant fields to consider. These can mean various things ranging from customer behaviour analysis to robotics. Many respondents see Emotion AI's potential in increasing engagement, enabling personalized interactions, and enhancing user experiences. There is a clear demand for applied, use-case driven modules, such as different practical contexts where it has been found useful.

To add another layer to the relevance of the offered course list and reflect on the results of the questionnaire-based needs assessment, Figure 7. links the most important skills with the courses that contribute to their acquisition/development.

Figure 7: Stakeholders top desired skills of an Emotion AI specialist connected to the final list of self-standing learning modules. For the sake of clear visualisation only the first 6 (most voted) skills are connected to the courses.

To stand out from the other AI-related training offerings, we will be using the key areas identified in the questionnaire results to be the foundation of the Emotion AI self-standing modules: AI fundamentals, human-centered skills, applied use cases, and ethics.

For the delivery of the self-standing modules, most respondents preferred short videos, slides or lecture notes, and continuous assessment. These will be the core structure of the modules, as time and resource constraints were the main barriers of why respondents have not adopted AI learning. To add additional flexibility, we will introduce micro-credentials allowing learners to earn certification after each module if they cannot complete the full basic or advanced certification path. Q&A sessions were rated as very valuable. If live sessions are conducted, Q&A sessions can be integrated into them.

Based on market analysis and internal discussions and needs identified during the SSLM development process, the team will also cover additional topics including *Introduction to*

Emotion AI, Using Emotion AI for UI/UX, Future of Emotion AI, Innovation and Entrepreneurship, Corporate Engagement, and Emotion and Multimodal Foundation Models.

3. Curriculum design

3.1. Programme objectives

The objective is to develop and deliver at least 11 self-standing modules on Artificial Intelligence with a specific focus on Emotion AI, alongside two modules on innovation, entrepreneurship, and ethics. The modules aim to address the skills needs of Europe in these emerging technologies, and provide state-of-the-art, professionally curated knowledge and content from AI and Emotion AI to uplift the AI skills in Europe. Some of the modules can be incorporated as courses in the EIT Digital Master School's Emotion AI Master's degree program.

Students will learn a foundational understanding of Emotion AI, including its underlying technologies, application across sectors, ethical and societal considerations, and future developments. The modules are interdisciplinary, combining elements of artificial intelligence, cognitive science, engineering, research, and design.

The target audience of the modules is broad, including individuals with a background in IT, computer science, engineering, mathematics, and related fields, as well as those without degrees or prior experience in these areas. It also includes working professionals seeking to develop their AI skills and job seekers aiming to enter the field.

3.2. Self-standing modules and curriculum

The modules are based on the preliminary list of topics from the proposal. The list is updated according to labour market needs. Each module in curriculum has its own content, assessment, and learning objectives. They do not have to be followed in order and are independent of one another, unless specified in the module prerequisites.

The team envisage two levels of the SSLM curriculum: *basic* and *advanced*. Each of the levels has its own set of modules and they differ on the coverage of the topics and on the duration of the SSLM. *Basic* modules are intended for individuals with little or no background in technical fields that intend to acquire a preliminary knowledge on the

respective topics. The *advanced* modules are designed for individuals with a background in technical fields and are intended to acquire more deep knowledge on the topic.

The curriculums cover a wide range of topics that range from AI basics, such as basics of data analysis and machine learning, to more advanced topics of AI and Emotion AI, such as emotional human-robot interaction and analysis of multimodal input for emotion recognition. The curriculums have been designed to prepare learners with a solid foundation on AI and Emotion AI focusing on skills at different depth, extending learners' understanding for example by introducing more complex technical concepts in the advanced modules.

For some modules, both in the basic and advanced curriculum, we also envisaged different variants where each focus more on some of the respective aspects (e.g., use cases in one domain or another). Some of the modules are delivered by more than one instructor to also provide attendees the most appropriate and skilled person on the respective topics.

To deliver the SSLM the team evaluated the possible platforms available in the market including [Coursera](#), [Udemy](#) and a more recent platform [Icarus AI](#). Although, Coursera and Udemy are more accepted by companies, the team opted with Icarus AI which is committed to promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) in all aspects of their business. Icarus AI believe that a diverse workforce brings a variety of perspectives and experiences which is crucial to achieving their mission of providing accessible, high-quality education to learners around the world. Icarus AI strive to create an inclusive environment where all employees, partners, and learners feel valued, respected, and supported. Icarus AI is dedicated to ongoing education, training to ensure promotion of DEI in workplaces and in the education industry at large. Moreover, EITD has a strategic collaboration and direct contacts with the Icarus AI team to customize the platform to specific needs (e.g., create curriculum, group of modules, dependencies among modules, different assessment approaches, add specific certificates issued by EITD). The Icarus AI platform has been also successfully used for other similar projects funded by the EU (e.g., SPECTRO, RESHIP, ACHIEVE), with very positive feedback from the instructors. All the modules are available at this URL: <https://eit.icarus.education/emai4eu/>

3.2.1. Final list of modules

The market analysis carried out in WP1, and several discussions happened at WP2 level among the partners, and happened by each partner and their industrial contacts, revealed that the initial list of envisaged modules need to be extended to cover new emerging

technical and soft skills. To this extent, the following modules were added to the final list of modules: *Introduction to Emotion AI*, *Using Emotion AI for UI/UX*, *Future of Emotion AI*, *Emotion and Multimodal Foundation Models*, *Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, and *Corporate Engagement*.

We remark that, all the module titles are preliminary and are subject to change during the development phase, as well as during the following years to address possible feedback emerging from the envisaged evaluation questionnaires administered to the individuals attending each module.

Modules were allocated to partners through a voting process. Each partner indicated their willingness and expertise to develop each module, and the WP2 leader assigned modules based on the results. The consortium agreed that during the implementation of SSLMs, multiple partners would be given the opportunity to develop a specific topic. This is the case for the following courses: 1) the advanced "*Introduction to Emotion AI*" which is developed by University of Trento and by the University of Cote D'Azur; 2) the basic and advanced "*Creating Value for Humans through AI*" delivered by University of Rennes and Satlabs (for the basic versions) and Politecnico di Milano and Satlabs (for the advanced); 3) the basic of "*Basic of Data Analysis*" by University Politecnica of Madrid and Satlabs; 4) the advanced "Affective Computing" by Politecnico of Milano and Eötvös Loránd Tudományegyetem (ELTE).

The rationale for having different variant of the "same" course is to allow each to focus on specific aspects (e.g., practical vs theoretical, different application use cases like robotics and finance). These courses with the same name (at this stage) are separated in the current list (see Table 1.) by numbering after their titles, and the team will subsequently make the course titles unique.

Basic (short)	Advanced (long)
1. Analysis of Multimodal Input for Emotion Recognition	18. Analysis of Multimodal Input for Emotion Recognition
2. Session-based Detection of User Profile and Emotions	19. Session-based Detection of User Profile and Emotions
3. Emotional Human-Robot Interaction	20. Affective Computing
4. Affective Computing	21. Affective Computing (II)
5. Cognitive Science	22. Basics of Data Analysis
6. Basics of Data Analysis	23. Semantic Web Technologies
7. Semantic Web Technologies	24. Creating Value for Humans Through AI
8. Creating Value for Humans Through AI	25. Deep Network Development
9. Natural Language Processing	26. Machine Learning
10. Machine Learning	27. Ethics for Trustworthy AI (Emotion AI Ethics)
11. Ethics for Trustworthy AI	28. Introduction to Emotion AI
12. Introduction to Emotion AI	29. Using Emotion AI for UI/UX
13. Introduction to Emotion AI (II)	30. Future of Emotion AI
14. Using Emotion AI for UI/UX	31. Innovation and Entrepreneurship
15. Future of Emotion AI	32. Emotion and Multimodal Foundation Models
16. Innovation and Entrepreneurship	
17. Corporate Engagement	

Table 1: Overview of Emotion AI modules for Basic and Advanced levels

3.2.2. Micromodules

A micromodule is the basic content unit of the self-standing learning modules. It is a meaningful, manageable amount of comprehensible learning material related to the main topic of the module. Each self-standing learning module may contain a different number of micro-modules, depending on the course developer's vision.

However, despite the flexibility allowed, the team considered it useful to apply a uniform framework, which means the following preliminary content recommendations: 3 to 10 minutes of video, approx. 10 minutes of independent learning material, and approx. 10 minutes of quiz per micromodule. Basic level modules contain 10-12 micromodules, while advanced level modules contain 20-24 micromodules.

3.3. Module template

All responsible partners used the same template to develop the self-standing learning modules' syllabus. This document, provided in Appendix 3, includes the following components:

- Module information
 - Title, difficulty level, Responsible Partner info
- Module description
 - Target audience
 - Related Master's Programme (if any)
 - Prerequisites
 - Connected Learning Path*
 - Learning objectives
 - Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)
 - Overarching Learning Objectives (OLOs)
- Teaching and Learning methods
- Structure
- Schedule
- Assessment and grading procedures
- Information for successful completion

* The connected learning path is linked to obtaining the basic certificate and the advanced certificate. More information about the certificates can be found in section 3.6. We remark that the learning paths may be subject to revision in the remaining part of the project to take into account the possible feedback emerged from the first period of delivery of the modules.

3.4. Self-standing learning module descriptions

3.4.1. Basic modules

Analysis of Multimodal Input for Emotion Recognition

This module examines the integration of multiple data sources such as visual, auditory, textual, and physiological—to recognize and interpret emotions using AI. Students explore data fusion strategies, signal processing, and machine learning models to build robust, multimodal emotion recognition systems.

Session-based Detection of Users Profile and Emotions

This module describes how session-based detection of user behaviour and emotions can be used in an educational context and how feedback can be provided to learners. After completing the course, students will understand how session-based detection and feedback can be applied in a real-world educational setting. The module includes an example application designed to improve the communication skills of health professionals used in a clinical appointment. The application uses different modalities to analyse learner communication, such as facial movement, body language, and speech analysis.

Emotional Human-Robot Interactions

The module provides an overview of human-robot interaction (HRI), with a particular focus on the role of emotions. It introduces the concept of HRI and explains its significance in the modern technological and social environment.

The module examines the main methods and models used to measure human emotions and their effects, and then reviews the different types and classifications of robots. The content focuses on the mechanisms of robots' recognition of human emotions and the techniques used to convey emotional signals, such as voice, body language, and visual cues. The module also examines different types of robots and their capabilities.

It addresses the importance of trust and empathy in shaping the quality of interactions between humans and robots. Finally, the module highlights ethical issues related to HRI, encouraging reflection on the broader implications of emotional connections between humans and machines.

Affective Computing with Case Studies

Affective Computing examines the intersection of technology and human emotions. The basic, self-standing module (5–10 hours) introduces the core principles of the field and highlights real-world applications. It covers how emotions can be detected through facial expressions, speech, body posture, and gestures, and how artificial intelligence processes this information to infer a person's state of mind. The module also provides an overview of human emotion theory, the role of context in interpretation, and the foundations of emotional interaction, where machines are able not only to recognise emotions but also to respond to them in a natural and empathetic manner. The basic module includes reflection on ethical and societal implications.

Cognitive Science

This beginner-friendly, self-standing module introduces the core ideas of this yet novel and constantly expanding research field. By the end of the course, students will have acquired the fundamental knowledge to understand cognitive research and apply the respective ideas to artificial intelligence, another fast-growing field.

Basics of Data Analysis

This is a basic-level self-standing learning module on Basics on Data Analysis. Data analysis is the process of transforming raw information into meaningful insights through systematic exploration, organization, and interpretation. This beginner-friendly module (5–10 hours) provides an introduction to the main steps of data analysis: data collection, cleaning, descriptive statistics, visualization, simple models and simple interpretation. Learners will be introduced to essential concepts such as variables, distributions, correlations, and patterns, and will discover how data can be summarized both numerically and graphically.

The module emphasizes a hands-on and intuitive approach, designed for participants with no prior background in programming or statistics. Through real-world examples from domains such as healthcare, business, and social sciences, students will see how data analysis supports evidence-based decision-making and problem solving.

By the end of the course, students will have acquired the fundamental knowledge to:

- Understand the role of data analysis in different contexts.
- Recognize the key steps in a typical data analysis pipeline.
- Apply basic descriptive and visualization methods to small datasets.
- Appreciate the value of data-driven reasoning for everyday and professional challenges.

This course serves as a first step into the world of data analysis and prepares learners for more advanced modules, where more complex statistical and machine learning techniques will be introduced.

Semantic Web Technologies

This is a basic-level self-standing learning module on Knowledge Graphs. This module consists of 10 micromodules, which cover approx. 25 hours of high-quality learning material. One will learn the evolution of Semantic Web technologies since their inception in the early 2000s, finally arriving into the concept of knowledge graphs. The basic foundations for knowledge graphs will be explored, including data and knowledge representation languages (RDF, RDF Schema, SPARQL) and their different types of serialisations, as well as programming libraries for knowledge graph management (RDFLib). Then the learning module will move into discussing techniques for knowledge graph creation.

Creating Value for Humans Through AI

This course explores the emergence of Emotional Artificial Intelligence (EAI) as both a technological innovation and a societal phenomenon. Students will examine how conversational agents and affective computing simulate empathy, companionship, and social presence, shaping new relational norms in everyday life, education, healthcare, and professional contexts. Through the study of media narratives and real-world applications, the module highlights how emotional AI is framed as a promise of enhanced efficiency, personalization, and accessibility, while also becoming increasingly embedded in organizational practices and cultural habits.

At the same time, the course engages with the risks and vulnerabilities revealed by these technologies. Issues such as dependency, illusion of authentic connection, exploitation of sensitive emotional data, and manipulation of attention are critically assessed. Particular attention is given to the ambivalence of emotional AI as both a potential tool for support

and a possible source of psychological or social harm, especially for vulnerable groups such as children, adolescents, or isolated individuals. These ambiguities are further situated within broader transformations of social norms, identity, and human autonomy in the digital age.

Finally, the course places emphasis on the ethical, economic, and regulatory tensions surrounding emotional AI. Students will investigate controversies on authenticity versus simulation, humanization versus dehumanization, and freedom versus affective influence. Case studies will shed light on the strategies of industrial actors, the responses of regulators, and the role of mediators such as educators, therapists, and journalists. By the end of the module, students will be equipped to critically analyse the promises and perils of emotional AI, and to reflect on the forms of governance, education, and ethical safeguards needed to channel its development responsibly.

Natural Language Processing

The aim of this course is to introduce the main symbolic AI and machine learning methods used to analyse, generate, process, and produce documents written in natural language.

This course will cover the main challenges involved in automatic text processing and present the key symbolic AI and machine learning techniques used to analyse, generate, and exploit natural language. The focus will be almost exclusively on written language processing.

Machine Learning

This is a basic-level self-standing learning module on Machine Learning. The module (5–10 hours) introduces the core principles of machine learning and its role in building data-driven applications. Students will learn the difference between supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning, as well as the key steps of a machine learning workflow: data preparation, model training, evaluation, and interpretation. The focus is on building an intuitive understanding of concepts, supported by simple examples and visual explanations rather than programming or mathematics.

By the end of the module, learners will:

- Understand what machine learning is and how it differs from traditional programming.
- Recognize the main types of machine learning problems.

- Appreciate how ML is used in everyday applications, from recommendation systems to healthcare.
- Identify basic ethical issues such as bias, fairness, and explainability.

Ethics for Trustworthy AI

This course introduces the core ethical challenges in artificial intelligence and equips learners with the tools to evaluate and design responsible AI systems.

Through twelve structured modules, students examine how bias, fairness, transparency, privacy, and accountability impact AI outcomes. Case studies and practical tools are used to explore real-world implications across domains such as hiring, lending, and policing. The course concludes with a capstone project where students conduct an ethical audit of an AI system.

Students will:

- Understand why ethics is essential in AI design and deployment
- Identify sources of bias in data, models, and decision processes
- Apply techniques for bias mitigation, transparency, and explainability
- Evaluate privacy and data ethics issues

Introduction to Emotion AI

This course introduces the foundations of Emotion AI and equips learners with the knowledge to understand, evaluate, and apply technologies that sense and respond to human emotions. Through twelve structured modules, students explore psychological theories of emotion and how AI systems analyse facial expressions, voice, text, and physiological signals. Applications in healthcare, education, and business are examined alongside cultural and ethical concerns.

The course concludes with a capstone project where students critically evaluate a real-world Emotion AI product.

Students will:

- Understand the concept and goals of Emotion AI
- Learn core psychological theories of emotion
- Explore how AI detects emotions from faces, voices, text, and biosignals
- Gain insight into datasets, labeling, and machine learning for affective systems

- Analyse applications in healthcare, education, and business contexts
- Recognize cultural and ethical challenges, including consent, bias, and manipulation
- Critically assess the technical limits and social risks of Emotion AI
- Conduct a structured evaluation of an existing Emotion AI product

Introduction to Emotion AI (II)

Preliminary sessions for this module include:

- Introduction to emotions
- Emotions as feelings
- Emotions as cognitive patterns
- Emotions as motivation for decision-making process
- Emotions and philosophy
- Emotions as values
- Emotions and non-verbal communication
- Non-verbal communication signs
- Computational affectiveness
- Conclusions

Using Emotion Design for UX/UI

By the end of this module, learner possess a comprehensive skill set that bridges psychology, design, and technology. These competencies will enable learner to create emotionally intelligent digital experiences that resonate with users on a deeper level.

The learning objectives are as follows:

- Understand how emotions drive decision-making processes and shape digital experiences, from first impressions to long-term engagement patterns.
- Learn to integrate Emotional Design strategies into digital products in ways that align directly with business metrics and organizational goals.
- Design intelligent interfaces that can identify and respond dynamically to users' emotional states using cutting-edge Emotion AI technologies.
- Evaluate the emotional quality of digital experiences using established models, specialized tools, and measurable KPIs to drive continuous improvement.

Using Emotion Design for UX/UI (II)

This module explores how emotional design principles enhance user experience (UX) and interface design (UI). It provides tools to understand user emotions and to intentionally design interactions that evoke positive, memorable experiences aligned with business goals.

Future of Emotion AI

The basic learning module explores the future technological prospects and applications of Emotion AI. They focus on future use cases and how this technology can change how humans interact with computers, such as enhancing usability and user experience, providing personalized motivation, and assisting and supporting people in their daily lives.

Innovation and Entrepreneurship

This module transforms innovation from abstract concept into structured practice. Through hands-on application of entrepreneurial frameworks, learner develop the critical thinking and execution skills needed to identify genuine opportunities, validate assumptions, and bring ideas to market with confidence

A comprehensive self-standing module designed to equip students and early-career professionals with the essential skills to innovate, validate ideas, and launch successful ventures in today's dynamic digital landscape

The learning objectives are as follows:

- Learn systematic approaches to innovation that go beyond brainstorming, including design thinking methodologies and frameworks used by leading organizations worldwide.
- Master proven tools for identifying market gaps, validating customer needs, and transforming insights into actionable opportunities with measurable potential.
- Take ideas from initial discovery through prototyping, testing, refinement, and ultimately to a comprehensive go-to-market strategy ready for execution.
- Build the confidence and capabilities required to launch your own venture or drive transformative innovation within existing organizations.

Innovation and Entrepreneurship (II)

This module explores the principles and practices of innovation and entrepreneurship in the digital era. It enables students to identify opportunities, validate ideas, and design business models that align with market needs and emerging technologies.

Corporate Engagement

This program equips startups and SMEs with the skills to develop partnerships with corporates in the B2B space. It covers how to identify the right corporate targets, leverage Open Innovation programs, build an engagement strategy, sell effectively to corporates, manage the engagement process, and measure success.

3.4.2. Advanced modules

Analysis of Multimodal Input for Emotion Recognition

The Emotion Identification through Biological Signals (EIBS) module introduces students to advanced methods in affective computing for the analysis and recognition of human emotions from biological signals. The course covers state-of-the-art approaches for feature extraction from physiological and behavioural data, with a focus on tools and practical techniques to link biological responses to emotional states. Designed for students with prior knowledge in artificial intelligence and basic programming, the module aims to provide hands-on skills for research and the development of intelligent systems sensitive to human behaviour.

Session-based Detection of Users Profile and Emotions

This module covers the entire process of designing and developing session-based detection of user behaviour and emotion in an educational setting. The module covers user research, idea development, design, and user testing for such applications. The module examines real-time detection system and the critical factors affecting sessions-based detection outcomes, such as cultural and individual variations, privacy, and ethical considerations.

Affective Computing

This online module provides hands-on training in the use of state-of-the-art open-source tools for extracting features of human behaviour. Through tutorials with screen recordings, participants will learn how to apply OpenFace, OpenPose, and openSMILE for behavioural

data analysis. The module also includes lectures on multimodal analysis of the extracted data, offering both theoretical background and practical guidance.

Advanced Affective Computing (II)

The advanced module expands on the foundation with approximately 10–20 hours of learning material. In addition to the concepts introduced at the basic level, it offers in-depth analysis of the complex dynamics of emotional interactions. Case studies inspired by real-world scenarios, including the Turing test and the COVID-19 pandemic, illustrate how emotion AI and affective computing function in practical and socially relevant contexts. The advanced module provides a comprehensive understanding of how affective computing is shaping domains such as healthcare, education, gaming, and assistive technologies.

Basics of Data Analysis

This is an advanced-level self-standing learning module on Basics on Data Analysis. Building upon the foundations of introductory data analysis, this module (10–20 hours) explores more advanced analytical techniques and their application to complex, real-world datasets. The course deepens the understanding of multivariate analysis, predictive modeling, and unsupervised learning, covering methods such as regression, classification, clustering, dimensionality reduction, and model evaluation. It also addresses practical challenges commonly encountered in applied data analysis, including handling missing values, managing class imbalance, ensuring reproducibility, and interpreting results critically.

A strong emphasis is placed on bridging theory and practice: each concept is accompanied by illustrative examples, case studies, and opportunities for hands-on exploration. Learners will be exposed to how advanced data analysis techniques are applied across different domains, from healthcare to finance and social sciences, highlighting the transformative role of data in research and industry.

By the end of the course, students will:

- Acquire methodological knowledge for conducting advanced analyses on structured datasets.
- Be able to critically interpret and validate results using statistical reasoning and evaluation metrics.
- Develop skills in applying data analysis tools to real-world problems.
- Gain awareness of the limitations, ethical aspects, and best practices for responsible data analysis.

- This module equips participants with the competencies necessary to work independently on data-driven projects and lays the foundation for further specialization in fields such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and computational modelling.

Semantic Web Technologies

This is an advanced-level self-standing learning module on Knowledge graphs. This module consists of 7 micromodules, which cover approx. 25 hours of high-quality learning material. One will learn how to create knowledge graphs from different types of heterogeneous data sources (tabular and non-tabular), how to ensure their quality using SHACL, and how to exploit them in applications. Additional aspects that will be covered in the course are related to the interaction between knowledge graphs and large language models (LLMs), including how to generate SPARQL queries for a given knowledge graph from natural language queries, as well as knowledge graph embeddings.

Creating Value for Humans Through AI

The course will focus on understanding the nuances of interactive AI-based systems, their benefits for the final users, and the potential problems they can generate if they are naively designed. The emphasis will be on understanding how Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) principles and methods can help design “human-centered” AI systems, which implies considering who AI systems are built for, designing AI models that can intrinsically support transparency, and evaluating through proper methods how well the resulting systems work with respect to user needs and expectations. After introducing the basic concepts of HCI, the course will focus on models, methods, and interaction paradigms peculiar to AI systems. The course includes a tutorial on designing and prototyping interfaces for knowledge exploration using Large Language Models

Deep Network Development

The module provides an introduction to the principles and practices of deep learning and how to develop neural networks. The course will cover the fundamentals of neural networks (e.g., key architectures, training methods, and practical applications) and the libraries used to develop such models (e.g., PyTorch). At the end of the course, the attendees should be able to implement and test a deep neural network on a problem of choice.

The course will start from the basics before discussing more advanced topics. Thus, it is recommended to all beginners and practitioners interested in applying deep networks in their data processing pipelines.

Machine Learning

This is an advanced-level self-standing learning module on Machine Learning. The module (10-20 hours) builds on fundamental knowledge and focuses on the design, training, and evaluation of machine learning models. It explores major algorithms for classification, regression, clustering, and dimensionality reduction, as well as more specialized topics such as ensemble methods, neural networks, and deep learning basics. Learners will also be introduced to advanced concepts such as model evaluation metrics, hyperparameter tuning, and cross-validation.

By the end of the course, participants will:

- Gain knowledge of the mathematical foundations and algorithmic principles behind common ML methods.
- Apply advanced techniques to real-world datasets and critically interpret results.
- Understand model selection, validation, and optimization strategies.
- Reflect on the challenges of fairness, transparency, and ethical deployment of ML systems.

Emotion AI Ethics

Your elderly mother lives alone and suffers moderate depression which is easily remedied by a short telephone call from you. The problem is, you cannot be calling all the time. But, an AI agent trained to speak as you do and with your voice could fill the gaps. You could arrange for automatic calls, and your mother would never know the difference. She would only know she is happier. Do you do it?

There is no right or wrong answer, but there are better and worse understandings of what is at stake. By investigating the principles of AI ethics and their applications in the real world, we will learn how to understand and justify the difficult human decisions surrounding today's technology.

Outcomes:

- Learn the fundamental principles of AI ethics: Autonomy, Dignity, Privacy, Fairness, Equity, Social wellbeing, Explainability, Safety, Performance.

- Understand how to apply the principles in the real world, with an emphasis on the tools of emotion AI.

Introduction to Emotion AI

Core Competencies Learner Develop:

- Emotional psychology foundations: Understanding emotional models, facial action coding, vocal tone patterns, and physiological responses
- Technical skill sets: Computer vision for facial expression analysis, voice analysis techniques, natural language processing for sentiment detection, and physiological sensing methods
- Evaluation expertise: Model performance assessment, bias detection, risk assessment frameworks, and validation strategies
- Business acumen: Connecting emotional insights to measurable business outcomes, user engagement metrics, and strategic product differentiation

The learning objectives are as follows:

- Understand what Emotion AI is, its historical development, and its growing impact across industries and society
- Learn the emotional psychology theories and technical methodologies used to detect and interpret human emotions
- Recognize opportunities to integrate Emotion AI into products and services that enhance user experience and business value
- Develop Emotion AI solutions responsibly with awareness of privacy, bias, consent, and regulatory compliance

Introduction to Emotion AI (II)

This module provides an introduction to Emotion AI and its role in digital products and services. Students explore the psychological and technical foundations of recognizing and interpreting emotions through artificial intelligence. The course also addresses ethical considerations and industry applications.

Using Emotion Design for UX/UI

This advanced module was developed by LUDOTIC, our partner specialising in UX/UI Design and Human Computer Interaction.

This module helps to understand the changes brought by emotional AI to the field of UX/UI design. The target audience is UX/UI professionals, Front-End developers, people in charge of HCI.

After reviewing key concepts of cognitive ergonomics (human perception, human information processing, problem solving, human errors...), the module outlines the benefits and the points of caution related to the recognition of human emotions and the use of simulated emotions by AI in the context of human-machine interaction.

Future of Emotion AI

This course explores the Emotion AI today and how we are transitioning to future applications of Emotion AI and its potential to change how humans interact with computers. Course will look at the cutting-edge directions of Emotion AI, such as Emotion AI as assistive tool and critical issues associated with Emotions AI.

Innovation and Entrepreneurship

This module is designed to examine the themes of innovation and entrepreneurship, with particular attention to the interconnections between these two concepts. It is organized into four sections, each comprising five lessons.

The pedagogical approach is structured as follows: first, to define and contextualize the notion of innovation, including the environments and circumstances in which it occurs; second, to interpret innovation as the outcome of investment in capital, with a particular focus in this module on intangible capital; third, to analyse the processes of value creation, with innovation positioned at the core of these dynamics; and finally, to explore entrepreneurship within this broader framework of innovation.

Each lesson will be supported by a video resource, complementary documentation (including excerpts from books and scholarly articles), and assessment tools.

Emotion and Multimodal Foundation Models

The module will provide an introduction to multimodal foundation models and their application for emotion analyses. The course will cover both how these models are developed and their potential (and limitations) when queried about emotions. At the end of the course, the attendees should have the tools to understand which foundation models better suit their application needs, and how to use it.

The course will start from the basics before discussing more advanced topics. Thus, it is recommended to all beginners and practitioners interested in applying multimodal foundation models for analysing emotions.

3.5. Assessment and grading procedures

Given the original purpose of online courses, which focuses on self-paced independent learning and professional development, an asynchronous online delivery for the evaluation of the modules was preferred.

Considering the features of the EIT Digital Icarus Education platform, automatic evaluation of multiple-choice quizzes is the most common assessment method.

The pass threshold may vary for quizzes associated with individual micromodules and for quizzes associated with the entire module. In some cases, a score of over 70% is sufficient, while in others, only 100% completion is accepted.

3.6. Certification scheme

Certification is awarded upon the completion of either a single self-standing module or an entire specified certification path. For single self-standing modules, the certification is issued jointly by EIT Digital and the project partners. We remark that, although the University project partners contribute to the issuing of the certificates, these certificates might not be recognized by the Universities themselves as achieved CFUs to e.g., accelerate the respective master achievement.

The curriculum and its modules are organized into two certification paths: basic (entry-level) and advanced (expert-level). The basic path covers foundational topics, including core concepts, a comprehensive introduction, and essential skills, and it is designed for individuals who does not have a background in related fields. The entry-level learning path includes all the basic-level self-standing learning modules, that are the currently 17 modules that cover a wide range of topics, such as: data analysis, multimodal emotion recognition, cognitive science, affective computing, NLP, machine learning, ethics, UI/UX and emotion AI-related topic with the addition of business and entrepreneurship studies. (The current list of basic modules is available in Table 1.)

The advanced path addresses more complex subjects, specialized use cases, and technical aspects. It is an expert-level certification targeting individuals with a related degree, such as computer science or data analytics. Students must complete all modules and quizzes specified in the certification path to earn a certificate. Certification is awarded jointly by EIT Digital and project partners after successful completion of the final certification exam and/or a practical exam. The expert-level learning path covers all 15 advanced SSLMs, which are similar in topic to the basic level but double in content and expected learning hours. These provide high-quality, in-depth knowledge on selected scientific topics. The current list of advanced modules is available in Table 1.

The templates for the certificates are available in the Appendix 4. We may revise it during the remaining part of the project depending on the feedback we will receive.

3.7. Long-term plans for content updates

The team envisage the list of designed SSLMs as an evolving system that will learn from different sources. First, the individual SSLM evaluation questionnaires will be used to revise the contents and the presentation to address possible criticalities emerging from their analysis. Second, the instructors will update their courses to include possible new emerging contents to make the SSLM updated and attractive. Third, the team will continue to monitor the market through the companies participating to the consortium and the respective industrial contacts to identify any possible new skill of interest to then consider adding new SSLMs or revising existing ones.

3.8. Conclusions

The market analysis reveals a growing interest in Emotion AI, although the level of familiarity and understanding still varies across sectors. It also highlights a strong demand for both AI and emotion AI training. While stakeholders recognize the value of technical competencies, they also highlight the importance of human-centered skills and development of trustworthy and responsible AI and emotion AI systems. These findings confirm the need for a curriculum that integrates technical, ethical and interdisciplinary perspectives that align with the principles of the EU AI Act [12] and Digital Europe goals and supporting innovation in key industries in this emerging field.

The next steps involve piloting the SSLMs, collecting learners feedback, and revising the content and delivery as needed to ensure continued relevance and alignment with the market and professional standards. Beyond the piloting phase, the roadmap foresees

integrating the developed SSLMs into the Emotion AI Master's degree programme and lifelong learning offerings strengthening Europe's commitment to responsible and human-centric AI education.

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Appendix 1: Market Analysis Questionnaire

Emotion AI Training: Understanding Stakeholder Needs and Expectations

As part of the EMAI4EU project, we are gathering insights from a wide audience to better understand training needs and expectations in the field of Emotional Artificial Intelligence (Emotion AI).

Emotion Artificial Intelligence specialists for Europe (EMAI4EU), funded by the Digital Europe Programme of the European Commission, aims to train the next generation of specialists and innovators in Emotion Artificial Intelligence in Europe. In collaboration with partner universities and EIT Digital, we will create and deliver an online course on Emotion AI.

Emotion AI is a branch of artificial intelligence that focuses on developing systems that can recognize, interpret, process, and simulate human emotions and behaviour. These emotionally intelligent systems enable more natural, intuitive, and empathetic interactions between the users and the systems. Emotion AI systems can rely on technologies such as facial movement recognition, physiological sensors, voice analysis, and natural language processing. As a rapidly growing field, Emotion AI demands expertise in a wide range of areas, such as machine learning, psychology, and human-centered design.

This questionnaire is intended for both individuals and company representatives. Based on your role, some questions will be tailored to gather insights most relevant to your experience.

More information about the project can be found at: <https://www.eitdigital.eu/eu-collaborations/emai4eu/>

Introduction

All data collected will be used exclusively for research purposes. By participating in this questionnaire, you consent to the use of your responses for research analysis. The analysis of your answers is anonymous.

- 1) Are you ready to start the questionnaire? (Average time: 20 min)
 - a) No
 - b) Yes

- 2) Are you completing this questionnaire as an individual or as a representative of a company?
- a) Individual
 - b) Company representative

SECTION 2A: General information

- 3) What best describes your current role?
- a) Account manager
 - b) Accountant
 - c) Administrative assistant
 - d) C-Level/Top management
 - e) Customer service representative
 - f) Digital marketing specialist
 - g) Financial analyst
 - h) Graphic designer
 - i) Human resources
 - j) Internal auditor
 - k) Legal counsel
 - l) Maintenance technician
 - m) Management and general administration
 - n) Marketing manager
 - o) Operations manager
 - p) Project manager
 - q) Sales coordinator
 - r) Salesperson
 - s) Software developer
 - t) Software engineer
 - u) System administrator
 - v) Translator
 - w) UX design/research
 - x) Employee
 - y) Student
 - z) Freelancer

aa) Other:

4) Sector of activity

- a) Education
- b) Public administration
- c) Energy and utilities
- d) Finance and insurance
- e) Food and beverage
- f) Healthcare and pharmaceuticals
- g) Information technology and communications
- h) Manufacturing industry
- i) Professional services
- j) Real estate and construction
- k) Retail and e-commerce
- l) Tourism and hospitality
- m) Transportation and logistics
- n) Other:

5) Do you personally use AI tools or systems in your work tasks?

- a) Yes
- b) No

6) If yes, what do you use? (*Select all that apply*)

- a) Text generation (ChatGPT, Monica...)
- b) Image generation (DALL-E, MidJourney...)
- c) Data analysis (Tableau, Power BI...)
- d) Search engine (Gemini, Bing...)
- e) Video tools (Fliki, Piggy...)
- f) Programming (Copilot, Cursor...)
- g) Other:

7) If not, how do you think AI tools could be useful in your work?

SECTION 3A: Emotion AI

Emotion AI is a branch of artificial intelligence that focuses on developing systems that can recognize, interpret, process, and simulate human emotions and behavior. These emotionally intelligent systems enable more natural, intuitive, and empathetic interactions between the users and the systems. Emotion AI systems can rely on technologies such as facial movement recognition, physiological sensors, voice analysis, and natural language processing. As a rapidly growing field, Emotion AI demands expertise in a wide range of areas, such as machine learning, psychology, and human-centered design.

- 8) Have you heard of Emotion AI before taking this questionnaire?
- a) Yes
 - b) No
- 9) Emotion AI technology will become increasingly important in my sector over the next few years. *Please rate your level of agreement on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Strongly disagree' and 7 means 'Strongly agree'.*
- a) 1
 - b) 2
 - c) 3
 - d) 4
 - e) 5
 - f) 6
 - g) 7
 - h) I don't know
- 10) Are there any areas where you think Emotion AI could have a significant impact but is not currently being used?
- 11) How important do you consider each of the following skills for an Emotion AI specialist? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.*
- a) Machine learning
 - b) Emotion recognition

- c) Signal processing
- d) Natural language processing (NLP)
- e) Computer vision
- f) Software development
- g) Data engineering
- h) Model evaluation and validation
- i) Systems design and architecture
- j) Human psychology understanding
- k) Empathy development
- l) Ethical decision-making
- m) Problem-solving
- n) Communication skills
- o) Other:

12) Are there any additional skills you believe are important for an Emotion AI specialist that are not listed above?

13) Currently, do you perceive Emotion AI as a technological bubble or as a valuable asset for society? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Technological bubble' and 7 means 'Valuable asset'.

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know

SECTION 4A: Training

14) Would you personally be interested in training related to AI? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not interested' and 7 means 'Interested'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know yet

15) Would you personally be interested in training specifically focused on Emotion AI (emotion recognition, computer vision, physiological monitoring, etc.)? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not interested' and 7 means 'Interested'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know yet

16) What are your main challenges when it comes to learning or adopting AI in your work? (e.g., time, cost, lack of support, lack of resources, other, etc.)

17) Which pricing model would you personally prefer for online courses?

- a) One-time payment
- b) Subscription based
- c) I don't know
- d) Other

- 18) How much would you personally be willing to pay for a full online course (about 13 modules) on Emotion AI?
- a) 0-25 €
 - b) 26-50 €
 - c) 51-200 €
 - d) 201-500 €
 - e) 500+ €
 - f) It depends on the value and contents of the course
- 19) How important is each of the following types of Emotion AI certification to you? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.*
- a) Industry-recognized certification
 - b) University-issued certification
 - c) Both are equally valuable
 - d) Emotion AI certification is not important for me
- 20) Would you prefer learning paths for: *(Select all that apply)*
- a) Different skill levels (e.g., introductory, intermediate, advanced)
 - b) Technical aspects (e.g., data analysis, AI models)
 - c) Applied use cases (e.g., healthcare, HR, marketing)
 - d) Role-specific (e.g., developer, designer, researcher)
- 21) How important do you consider each of the following topics for Emotion AI online course? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.*
- a) Analysis of Multimodal Input for Emotion Recognition
 - b) Session-based detection of user profile and emotions
 - c) Emotional Human-Robot Interaction
 - d) Affective Computing

- e) Cognitive Science
- f) Introduction to human-machine socio-emotional interaction
- g) Basics of Data Analysis
- h) Semantic Web Technologies
- i) Creating Value for Humans through AI
- j) Deep Network Development
- k) Natural Language Processing
- l) Machine Learning
- m) Ethics for Trustworthy AI
- n) Introduction to Emotion AI
- o) Using Emotion AI for UI/UX
- p) Evaluation on AI methods
- q) Future of Emotion AI

22) Can you think of additional modules or topics that would be valuable for you?

23) Which learning format do you prefer? (*Select all that apply*)

- a) Synchronous (live sessions)
- b) Asynchronous (self-paced course material)
- c) Blended learning (combination of synchronous and asynchronous)
- d) Other:

24) What type of course materials would you like to have access to? (*Select all that apply*)

- a) Slides and lecture notes
- b) Articles and reading list
- c) Code examples
- d) Short videos with concrete examples (15 min)
- e) Other

25) How valuable would personalized Q&A sessions be in your learning experience?

- a) Extremely valuable

- b) Somewhat valuable
- c) Not very valuable
- d) Not necessary

26) What type of assessment do you find most effective?

- a) Continuous assessment (quizzes and tasks)
- b) Final exam at the end
- c) Both
- d) I don't know

SECTION 2B: General information

27) Sector of activity

- a) Education
- b) Public administration
- c) Energy and utilities
- d) Finance and insurance
- e) Food and beverage
- f) Healthcare and pharmaceuticals
- g) Information technology and communications
- h) Manufacturing industry
- i) Professional services
- j) Real estate and construction
- k) Retail and e-commerce
- l) Tourism and hospitality
- m) Transportation and logistics
- n) Other:

28) Number of Employees

- a) 1-20
- b) 21-99
- c) 100-249

d) 250+

29) What is your current role within the company?

- a) Account manager
- b) Accountant
- c) Administrative assistant
- d) C-Level/Top management
- e) Customer service representative
- f) Digital marketing specialist
- g) Financial analyst
- h) Graphic designer
- i) Human resources
- j) Internal auditor
- k) Legal counsel
- l) Maintenance technician
- m) Management and general administration
- n) Marketing manager
- o) Operations manager
- p) Project manager
- q) Sales coordinator
- r) Salesperson
- s) Software developer
- t) Software engineer
- u) System administrator
- v) Translator
- w) UX design/research
- x) Employee
- y) Student
- z) Freelancer
- aa) Other

30) Do you personally use AI tools or systems in your work tasks?

- a) Yes
- b) No

31) If yes, what do you use? (*Select all that apply*)

- a) Text generation (ChatGPT, Monica...)
- b) Image generation (DALL-E, MidJourney...)
- c) Data analysis (Tableau, Power BI...)
- d) Search engine (Gemini, Bing...)
- e) Video tools (Fliki, Piggy...)
- f) Programming (Copilot, Cursor...)
- g) Other

32) If not, how do you think AI tools could be useful in your work?

33) Is your company currently using any AI technology? *Please rate your company's current level of AI integration on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not currently using' and 7 means 'Fully integrated'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know

SECTION 3B: Emotion AI

Emotion AI is a branch of artificial intelligence that focuses on developing systems that can recognize, interpret, process and simulate human emotions and behavior. These emotionally intelligent systems enable more natural, intuitive, and empathetic interactions between the users and the systems. Emotion AI systems can rely on technologies such as facial movement recognition, physiological sensors, voice analysis, and natural language

processing. As a rapidly growing field, Emotion AI demands expertise in a wide range of areas, such as machine learning, psychology, and human-centered design.

34) Have you heard of Emotion AI before taking this questionnaire?

- a) Yes
- b) No

35) Emotion AI technology will become increasingly important in my sector over the next few years. *Please rate your level of agreement on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Strongly disagree' and 7 means 'Strongly agree'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know

36) For you, what priority will Emotion AI have in your company? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Low priority' and 7 means 'High priority'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know

37) Are there any areas in your company where you think Emotion AI could have significant impact but is not currently being used?

- 38) Are there any areas outside your company where you think Emotion AI could have significant impact but is not currently being used?
- 39) Currently, do you perceive Emotion AI as a technological bubble or as a valuable asset for society? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Technological bubble' and 7 means 'Valuable asset'.
- a) 1
 - b) 2
 - c) 3
 - d) 4
 - e) 5
 - f) 6
 - g) 7
 - h) I don't know

SECTION 4B: Needs and priorities

- 40) What potential benefits do you foresee from using Emotion AI technologies in your business operations? (*Select all that apply*)
- a) Enhanced mental health support
 - b) Increased engagement
 - c) Enhanced empathy
 - d) Reduced stress levels
 - e) Personalized interactions
 - f) Better decision making
 - g) Improved customer satisfaction
 - h) Enhanced productivity
 - i) More authentic communication
 - j) Improved team collaboration
 - k) Enhanced user experience
 - l) Improving recruitment
 - m) No specific benefit

n) Other:

41) Would you like to have an Emotion AI specialist in your company? An Emotion AI specialist has the general and comprehensive knowledge required of an AI professional, but also the skills needed to work with sensitive data, ethical and legal regulations, design human-centered solutions, manage common emotional states and create affective systems.

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) I don't know yet

42) If yes, how soon do you anticipate the need for an Emotion AI specialist in your company?

- a) Month
- b) Semester
- c) A year
- d) More than a year
- e) I don't know
- f) Other:

43) If not, what is holding you back or preventing you?

44) How important do you consider each of the following skills for an Emotion AI specialist?

Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.

- a) Machine learning
- b) Emotion recognition
- c) Signal processing
- d) Natural language processing (NLP)
- e) Computer vision
- f) Software development

- g) Data engineering
- h) Model evaluation and validation
- i) Systems design and architecture
- j) Human psychology understanding
- k) Empathy development
- l) Ethical decision-making
- m) Problem-solving
- n) Communication skills
- o) Other

45) Are there any additional skills you believe are important for an Emotion AI specialist that are not listed above?

SECTION 5B: Training

46) Does your company support employees in pursuing additional AI certifications or continuous learning opportunities in the field of AI?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) I Don't Know

47) Would you personally be interested in training related to AI? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not interested' and 7 means 'Interested'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know yet

48) Would you personally be interested in training specifically focused on Emotion AI (emotion recognition, computer vision, physiological monitoring, etc.)? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not interested' and 7 means 'Interested'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know yet

49) How relevant is AI training for your company's goals? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not relevant' and 7 means 'Very relevant'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know

50) How relevant is Emotion AI training for your company's goals? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not relevant' and 7 means 'Very relevant'.*

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5
- f) 6
- g) 7
- h) I don't know

51) What are your main challenges when it comes to learning or adopting AI in your work? (e.g., time, cost, lack of support, lack of resources, other, etc.)

a) Free text

52) Which pricing model would your company prefer for online courses?

a) One-time payment

b) Subscription based without any engagement of duration

c) I don't know

d) Other:

53) How much would you personally be willing to pay for a full online course (about 13 modules) on Emotion AI?

a) 0-25 €

b) 26-50 €

c) 51-200 €

d) 201-500 €

e) 500+ €

f) It depends on the value and contents of the course

54) How important is each of the following types of Emotion AI certification for your company? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.*

a) Industry-recognized certification

b) University-issued certification

c) Both are equally valuable

d) Emotion AI certification is not important for our company

55) Would you prefer learning paths for: *(Select all that apply)*

a) Different skill levels (introductory, intermediate, advanced)

- b) Technical aspects (data analysis, AI models)
- c) Applied use cases (healthcare, HR, marketing)
- d) Role-specific (developer, designer, researcher)

56) How important do you consider each of the following topics for Emotion AI online course? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.*

- a) Analysis of Multimodal Input for Emotion Recognition
- b) Session-based detection of user profile and emotions
- c) Emotional Human-Robot Interaction
- d) Affective Computing
- e) Cognitive Science
- f) Introduction to human-machine socio-emotional interaction
- g) Basics of Data Analysis
- h) Semantic Web Technologies
- i) Creating Value for Humans through AI
- j) Deep Network Development
- k) Natural Language Processing
- l) Machine Learning
- m) Ethics for Trustworthy AI
- n) Introduction to Emotion AI
- o) Using Emotion AI for UI/UX
- p) Evaluation on AI methods
- q) Future of Emotion AI

57) Can you think of additional modules or topics that would be valuable for you?

58) Which learning format do you prefer? *(Select all that apply)*

- a) Synchronous (live sessions)
- b) Asynchronous (self-paced course material)
- c) Blended learning (combination of synchronous and asynchronous)
- d) Other:

59) What type of course materials would you like to have access to? (*Select all that apply*)

- a) Slides and lecture notes
- b) Articles and reading list
- c) Code examples
- d) Short videos with concrete examples (15 min)
- e) Other:

60) How valuable would personalized Q&A sessions be in your learning experience?

- a) Extremely valuable
- b) Somewhat valuable
- c) Not very valuable
- d) Not necessary

61) What type of assessment do you find most effective?

- a) Continuous assessment (quizzes and tasks)
- b) Final exam at the end
- c) Both
- d) I don't know

Conclusion

Thank you for your participation. Your responses are invaluable and provide important insights into opinions and perspectives on the topic of Emotional Artificial Intelligence. Your contribution will help enrich our understanding and guide our future actions. We appreciate your involvement and interest in this research.

62) If you have additional comments or ideas to share with us, please feel free to send us a comment.

If you know someone who might be interested in this topic or this questionnaire, please feel free to share it.

Appendix 2: Market analysis questionnaire results

1. Are you ready to start the questionnaire? (Average time: 15 min)

[More details](#)

● No 7
● Yes 151

2. Are you completing this questionnaire as an individual or as a representative of a company?

[More details](#)

● Individual 106
● Company representative 45

3. What best describes your current role?

[More details](#)

4. Sector of activity

[More details](#)

Education	16
Public administration	6
Energy and utilities	2
Finance and insurance	4
Food and beverage	0
Healthcare and pharmaceuticals	12
Information technology and communications	26
Manufacturing industry	12
Professional services	9
Real estate and construction	0
Retail and e-commerce	1
Tourism and hospitality	2
Transportation and logistics	2
Other	14

5. Do you personally use AI tools or systems in your work tasks?

[More details](#)

Yes	100
No	6

6. If yes, what do you use? (Select all that apply)

[More details](#)

Text generation (ChatGPT, Monica...)	95
Image generation (DALL-E, MidJourney...)	27
Data analysis (Tableau, Power BI...)	31
Search engine (Gemini, Bing...)	54
Video tools (Fliki, Piggy...)	5
Programming (Copilot, Cursor...)	47
Other	3

10. Are there any areas where you think Emotion AI could have significant impact but is not currently being used? [More details](#)

106
Responses

Latest Responses

"edtech"

"No"

...

13 respondents (12%) answered AI for this question.

11. How important do you consider each of the following skills for an Emotion AI specialist? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'. [More details](#)

● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 ● 6 ● 7

- Machine Learning
- Emotion recognition
- Signal processing
- Natural Language Processing
- Computer vision
- Software development
- Data engineering
- Model evaluation and validation
- Systems design and architecture
- Human psychology understanding
- Empathy development
- Ethical decision-making
- Problem-solving
- Communication skills

12. Are there any additional skills you believe are important for an Emotion AI specialist that are not listed above? [More details](#)

30
Responses

Latest Responses

"kindness"

...

4 respondents (13%) answered AI for this question.

13. Currently, do you perceive Emotion AI as a technological bubble or as a valuable asset for society? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Technological bubble' and 7 means 'Valuable asset'. [More details](#)

14. Would you personally be interested in training related to AI? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not interested' and 7 means 'Interested'. [More details](#)

15. Would you personally be interested in training specifically focused on Emotion AI (emotion recognition, computer vision, physiological monitoring, etc.)? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not interested' and 7 means 'Interested'.

16. What are your main challenges when it comes to learning or adopting AI in your work? (e.g., time, cost, lack of support, lack of resources, other, etc.)

106 Responses

Latest Responses
 "lack of resources"
 "Diffidence"
 ...

35 respondents (33%) answered Time for this question.

17. Which pricing model would you personally prefer for online courses?

One-time payment	40
Subscription based	27
I don't know	35
Other	4

18. How much would you personally be willing to pay for a full online course (about 13 modules) on Emotion AI? [More details](#)

19. How important is each of the following types of Emotion AI certification to you? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'. [More details](#)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

Industry-recognized certification

University-issued certification

Both are equally valuable

Emotion AI certification is not important for me

20. Would you prefer learning paths for: (Select all that apply) [More details](#)

Different skill levels (e.g., introductory, intermediate, advanced)	66
Technical aspects (e.g., data analysis, AI models)	62
Applied use cases (e.g., healthcare, HR, marketing)	67
Role-specific (e.g., developer, designer, researcher)	59
Other	1

21. How important do you consider each of the following topics for Emotion AI online course? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.

[More details](#)

● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 ● 6 ● 7

- Analysis of Multimodal Input for Emotion Recognition
- Session-based Detection of User Profile and Emotions
- Emotional Human-Robot Interaction
- Affective Computing
- Cognitive Science
- Introduction to Human-Machine Socio-emotional Interaction
- Basics of Data Analysis
- Semantic Web Technologies
- Creating Value for Humans Through AI
- Deep Network Development
- Natural Language Processing
- Machine Learning
- Ethics for Trustworthy AI
- Introduction to Emotion AI
- Using Emotion AI for UI/UX
- Evaluation on AI Methods
- Future of Emotion AI

22. Can you think of additional modules or topics that would be valuable for you?

[More details](#)

21

Responses

Latest Responses

"ras"

...

3 respondents (14%) answered Emotion for this question.

23. Which learning format do you prefer? *(Select all that apply)*

[More details](#)

● Synchronous (live sessions)	31
● Asynchronous (self-paced course material)	40
● Blended learning (combination of synchronous and asynchronous)	59
● Other	2

24. What type of course materials would you like to have access to? *(Select all that apply)*

[More details](#)

● Slides and lecture notes	83
● Articles and reading list	51
● Code examples	53
● Short videos with concrete examples (15 min)	81
● Other	2

25. How valuable would personalized Q&A sessions be in your learning experience?

[More details](#)

● Extremely valuable	46
● Somewhat valuable	50
● Not very valuable	6
● Not necessary	4

26. What type of assessment do you find most effective?

[More details](#)

● Continuous assessment (quizzes and tasks)	56
● Final exam at the end	9
● Both	33
● I don't know	8

27. Sector of activity

[More details](#)

● Education	0
● Public administration	4
● Energy and utilities	1
● Finance and insurance	0
● Food and beverage	0
● Healthcare and pharmaceuticals	2
● Information technology and communications	21
● Manufacturing industry	4
● Professional services	4
● Real estate and construction	1
● Retail and e-commerce	0
● Tourism and hospitality	0
● Transportation and logistics	1
● Other	7

28. Number of Employees

[More details](#)

● 1-20	20
● 21-99	16
● 100-249	2
● 250+	7

29. What is your current role within the company?

[More details](#)

30. Do you personally use AI tools or systems in your work tasks?

[More details](#)

- Yes 42
- No 3

31. If yes, what do you use? (Select all that apply)

[More details](#)

Text generation (ChatGPT, Monica...)	39
Image generation (DALL-E, MidJourney...)	16
Data analysis (Tableau, Power BI...)	14
Search engine (Gemini, Bing...)	19
Video tools (Fliki, Piggy...)	2
Programming (Copilot, Cursor...)	11
Other	6

32. If not, how do you think AI tools could be useful in your work?

[More details](#)

3
Responses

Latest Responses

...

33. Is your company currently using any AI technology? Please rate your company's current level of AI integration on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not currently using' and 7 means 'Fully integrated'.

[More details](#)

1	7
2	12
3	5
4	2
5	10
6	3
7	4
I don't know	2

34. Have you heard of Emotion AI before taking this questionnaire?

[More details](#)

Yes	19
No	26

35. Emotion AI technology will become increasingly important in my sector over the next few years. *Please rate your level of agreement on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Strongly disagree' and 7 means 'Strongly agree'.*

[More details](#)

36. For you, what priority will Emotion AI have in your company? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Low priority' and 7 means 'High priority'.*

[More details](#)

37. Are there any areas in your company where you think Emotion AI could have significant impact but is not currently being used?

[More details](#)

45
Responses

Latest Responses

"support"

...

9 respondents (20%) answered customer for this question.

38. Are there any areas outside your company where you think Emotion AI could have significant impact but is not currently being used? [More details](#)

45
Responses

Latest Responses
"healthcare"
...

4 respondents (9%) answered emotions for this question.

39. Currently, do you perceive Emotion AI as a technological bubble or as a valuable asset for society? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Technological bubble' and 7 means 'Valuable asset'. [More details](#)

40. What potential benefits do you foresee from using Emotion AI technologies in your business operations? (Select all that apply)

41. Would you like to have an Emotion AI specialist in your company? An Emotion AI specialist has the general and comprehensive knowledge required of an AI professional, but also the skills needed to work with sensitive data, ethical and legal regulations, design human-centered solutions, manage common emotional states and create affective systems.

[More details](#)

Yes	9
No	12
I don't know yet	24

42. If yes, how soon do you anticipate the need for an Emotion AI specialist in your company?

[More details](#)

Month	1
Semester	1
A year	2
More than a year	2
I don't know	1
Other	2

43. If not, what is holding you back or preventing you?

[More details](#)

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Responses

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...

2 respondents (17%) answered à for this question.

présent questionnaire priority than other needs message crafted by AI early for our startup
 Mes réponses needs à de je early needs in our roadmap
 cherchent human interaction human Ma meaningless work titre personnel
 d'intelligence specialist would be better

44. How important do you consider each of the following skills for an Emotion AI specialist? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.

[More details](#)

● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 ● 6 ● 7

45. Are there any additional skills you believe are important for an Emotion AI specialist that are not listed above?

[More details](#)

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Responses

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...

4 respondents (40%) answered No for this question.

focus the risk **No** laws and regulations
 Multicultural background non Knowledge of laws
 risk of manipulation

46. Does your company support employees in pursuing additional AI certifications or continuous learning opportunities in the field of AI? [More details](#)

● Yes	20
● No	17
● I Don't Know	8

47. Would you personally be interested in training related to AI? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not interested' and 7 means 'Interested'. [More details](#)

● 1	3
● 2	0
● 3	2
● 4	2
● 5	12
● 6	10
● 7	13
● I don't know yet	3

48. Would you personally be interested in training specifically focused on Emotion AI (emotion recognition, computer vision, physiological monitoring, etc.)? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not interested' and 7 means 'Interested'. [More details](#)

● 1	3
● 2	4
● 3	4
● 4	5
● 5	10
● 6	8
● 7	7
● I don't know yet	4

49. How relevant is AI training for your company's goals? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not relevant' and 7 means 'Very relevant'.

[More details](#)

● 1	1
● 2	4
● 3	4
● 4	4
● 5	7
● 6	9
● 7	13
● I don't know	3

50. How relevant is Emotion AI training for your company's goals? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not relevant' and 7 means 'Very relevant'.

[More details](#)

● 1	5
● 2	7
● 3	5
● 4	4
● 5	6
● 6	7
● 7	6
● I don't know	5

51. What are your main challenges when it comes to learning or adopting AI in your work? (e.g., time, cost, lack of support, lack of resources, other, etc.)

[More details](#)

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"time cost, lack of resources"
...

23 respondents (51%) answered time for this question.

52. Which pricing model would your company prefer for online courses?

[More details](#)

● One-time payment	17
● Subscription based without any engagement of duration	8
● I don't know	18
● Other	2

53. How much would you personally be willing to pay for a full online course (about 13 modules) on Emotion AI?

[More details](#)

● 0-25 €	5
● 26-50 €	4
● 51-200 €	9
● 201-500 €	5
● 500+ €	3
● It depends on the value and contents of the course	19

54. How important is each of the following types of Emotion AI certification for your company? Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.

[More details](#)

● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 ● 6 ● 7

Industry-recognized certification
 University-issued certification
 Both are equally valuable
 Emotion AI certification is not important for our company

55. Would you prefer learning paths for: (Select all that apply)

[More details](#)

● Different skill levels (introductory, intermediate, advanced)	32
● Technical aspects (data analysis, AI models)	19
● Applied use cases (healthcare, HR, marketing)	27
● Role-specific (developer, designer, researcher)	15
● Other	1

56. How important do you consider each of the following topics for Emotion AI online course? *Please rate on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 means 'Not important' and 7 means 'Extremely important'.*

[More details](#)

● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 ● 6 ● 7

- Analysis of Multimodal Input for Emotion Recognition
- Session-based Detection of User Profile and Emotions
- Emotional Human-Robot Interaction
- Affective Computing
- Cognitive Science
- Introduction to Human-Machine Socio-emotional Interaction
- Basics of Data Analysis
- Semantic Web Technologies
- Creating Value for Humans Through AI
- Deep Network Development
- Natural Language Processing
- Machine Learning
- Ethics for Trustworthy AI
- Introduction to Emotion AI
- Using Emotion AI for UI/UX
- Evaluation on AI Methods
- Future of Emotion AI

57. Can you think of additional modules or topics that would be valuable for you?

[More details](#)

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Responses

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...

4 respondents (36%) answered no for this question.

none

Pas

no

Laws and regulations

non

58. Which learning format do you prefer? *(Select all that apply)*

[More details](#)

● Synchronous (live sessions)	9
● Asynchronous (self-paced course material)	20
● Blended learning (combination of synchronous and asynchronous)	26
● Other	0

59. What type of course materials would you like to have access to? *(Select all that apply)*

[More details](#)

● Slides and lecture notes	31
● Articles and reading list	14
● Code examples	14
● Short videos with concrete examples (15 min)	37
● Other	0

60. How valuable would personalized Q&A sessions be in your learning experience?

[More details](#)

● Extremely valuable	20
● Somewhat valuable	19
● Not very valuable	4
● Not necessary	2

61. What type of assessment do you find most effective?

[More details](#)

● Continuous assessment (quizzes and tasks)	28
● Final exam at the end	5
● Both	10
● I don't know	2

62. If you have additional comments or ideas to share with us, please feel free to send us a comment.

[More details](#)

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Responses

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...

4 respondents (20%) answered thanks for this question.

Word cloud containing the following terms: company will also be interested, AI declarations, security systems, learner's profile, people, topic, maybe having, lot of mistakes, emotional AI, strongly believe, development in this field, Confindustrial system, subject, best, systems, courses, EU, AI, thanks, and systems.

Appendix 3: Template for a self-standing module

Name of Module:	Credit Points (ECTS):	Module-ID:			
Person Responsible for module (Name, Mail address):					
University:			Department:		
1. Short description of the module					
2. Target audience					
3. The self-standing module is included in the following course/s of the Master's program (If not, add the text "N/A")					
4. Prerequisites for Participation (If not, add the text "N/A")					
5. The self-standing module belongs to the following Learning path/s (If not, add the text "N/A")					
6. Intended Learning Outcomes					
ILO	Description				
OLO	ILO1	ILO2	ILO3	ILO4	ILO5
	X	X			
			X		
					X

7. Teaching and Learning Methods

8. Structure (content, lessons, etc.)

Sessions	Descriptions, Content and materials

9. Schedule (course agenda and dates, including synchronous and asynchronous sessions)

Delivery	Sessions (in chronological order)	Hours	Dates
Asynchronous			
Synchronous			

Total 25 hours (1 ECTS) / 50 hours (2 ECTS)
 Number of hours in ASYNC delivery: X
 Number of hours in SYNC delivery: X

11. Assessment and Grading Procedures (describe the passing Threshold used)

12. Description about how can successfully complete the module to obtain the certificate (needs to be done in your self-standing module to obtain the certificate)

Appendix 4: Certification templates

Certification template for completing a single self-standing module:

THE EMAI4EU PROJECT PARTNERS AND EIT DIGITAL AWARD THIS CERTIFICATE TO

FULL NAME

upon successful completion of EIT Digital self-standing module: **NAME HERE**

Federico Menna
CEO, EIT Digital

TOMORROW'S DIGITAL INNOVATORS
AND ENTREPRENEURS

Certification template for completing a series of basic (entry-level) self-standing modules. The template has a cover page with the main information and a second page where the related (and completed) modules are listed:

EIT DIGITAL & THE EMAI4EU PROJECT PARTNERS AWARD THIS CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION FOR THE SERIES OF COURSES

AI BASICS

TO

FULL NAME

This is to certify that the participant has successfully completed all listed courses and passed the corresponding assessments, including the final evaluation.

Federico Menna
CEO, EIT Digital

TOMORROW'S DIGITAL INNOVATORS
AND ENTREPRENEURS

The participant has successfully completed all listed courses and passed the corresponding assessments, including the final evaluation.

AI courses:

Innovation & Entrepreneurship courses:

Certification template for completing a series of advanced (expert-level) self-standing modules. The template has a cover page with the main information and a second page where the related (and completed) modules are listed:

EIT DIGITAL & THE EMAI4EU PROJECT PARTNERS AWARD THIS CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION FOR THE SERIES OF COURSES

ADVANCED AI

TO

FULL NAME

This is to certify that the participant has successfully completed all listed courses and passed the corresponding assessments, including the final evaluation.

Federico Menna
CEO, EIT Digital

TOMORROW'S DIGITAL INNOVATORS
AND ENTREPRENEURS

The participant has successfully completed all listed courses and passed the corresponding assessments, including the final evaluation.

AI courses:

Innovation & Entrepreneurship courses:

